

A Study of Adjustment among 12th Standard Students

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ABSTRACT

The study was undertaken to study of Adjustment on Gender and Location among 12th standard students of district Jalna (M.S.). The sample of the study consisted 100 college students. Randomly selected from Difference College of Jalna District (M.S.). Bell's Adjustment Inventory by Lalit Sharma was used data collection. The data collected was statistically treated by using mean, SD and ANOVA. The findings of the study revealed that Male 12th standard college student's high adjustment than Female 12th standard college students. Urban 12th standard college student's high adjustment than rural 12th standard college students.

Keywords: Gender, Location, Adjustment, college students

INTRODUCTION

The term adjustment refers to the extent to which an individual's personality functions effectively in the world of people. It refers to the harmonious relationship between the person and the environment. In other words, it is the relationship that comes among the organisms, the environment and the personality. A well adjusted personality is well prepared to play the roles which are expected of the status assigned to him within given environment.

Adjustment, in psychology, the behavioral process by which humans and other animals maintain equilibrium among their various needs or between their needs and the obstacles of their environments. A sequence of adjustment begins when a need is felt and ends when it is satisfied. Hungry people, for example, are stimulated by their physiological state to seek food. When they eat, they reduce the stimulating

condition that impelled them to activity, and they are thereby adjusted to this particular need.

In general, the adjustment process involves four parts: (1) a need or motive in the form of a strong persistent stimulus, (2) the thwarting or no fulfillment of this need, (3) varied activity, or exploratory behavior accompanied by problem solving, and (4) some response that removes or at least reduces the initiating stimulus and completes the adjustment.

Adjustment is process in which a person varies his behavior to produce a more harmonious relationship between himself and his environment.

Coleman James c. "Adjustment is the outcomes of the individual's attempts to deal with stress and meet his needs also his effect to maintain harmonious relationship with the environment.

Adjustment is the relationship which comes to be established between the individual and the environment. Every individual plays certain position in his social relations. He is trained to play his role in such a way that his maximum needs will be fulfilled. So, he should play his role properly and get maximum satisfaction. If he does not play his role according to standards and training Home Environment received his needs may not be fulfilled and he may get frustrated.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Roy, Ekka and Ara(2011) observed that Girl students were better adjusted in all areas of adjustment than Boy students. Kurvilla (2006) reported that urban were well adjusted than rural students in all areas of adjustment problems. Enochs and Roland (2006)

studied (511) male and female university students in the first year, where he studied the nature of the environment, gender and the relation with level adjustment of social in the university, the result indicate out that males are more adjusted than females. Jain and Jandu (1998) conducted a study on adjustment areas on a sample of 240 students (14-19 years). Adjustment inventory for school students developed by Sinha and Singh (1984) was used to measure the adjustment of the students. They found that girls were better adjusted than boys. Thirugnana Sambadam (1990) also supported that boys were better adjusted than girls on a sample of 388 students of 9th grade.

Mohsin, et.al, (1985) have reported in a study conducted that male subjects have higher adjustment then female subject. Sulthana et.al (1981) conducted a comparative study on personality adjustment among rural and urban students. The sample of study consists of 200 urban and rural students study compared the adjustment of rural and urban group on social, emotional, health, home and family aspects. Results revealed that students of urban area were more adjusted as compared to rural college students.

Statement of the Problem

“A study of Adjustment among 12th standard college going students”

Objective of the Study

To examine the Gender, and Location in Adjustment among 12th standard college going students.

Hypothesis of the study

- 1) There is no significance difference between Adjustment than male and female 12th standard college students
- 2) There is no significance difference between Adjustment than Urban and Rural 12th standard college students

Methodology

Sample

The present study sample 100 was selected from college students of Jalna district in Maharashtra. The effective sample consisted of 100 subjects out of which 50 male students (25 urban and 25 rural students) and 50 female students (25 urban and 25 rural students). Stratified random sampling method

was employed to select the unit of sample. The subject selected in this sample will be used in the age group of 18 years to 21 years (Mean-18.63 and SD-1.90) and Ratio 1:1. Thus total sample includes as shown in the following table.

Gender

	Male	Female	Total
Urban	25	25	50
Rural	25	25	50
Total	50	50	100

Location

Research design

Research design to be implemented in the present research is as follow:

2x2 factorial designs use for the present study.

A

	A1	A2
B1	A1, B1	A2, B1
B2	A1, B2	A2, B2

B

A -Gender - A1- Male A2- female

B-Location - B1- Urban B2- Rural

Variables of the Study

Variables under study

Independent variables

1) Gender

- 1) Male
- 2) Female

2) Location

- 1) Urban
- 2) Rural

Dependents variables

Adjustment

Research Tool

Bell's Adjustment Inventory

Bell's adjustment was developed by Lalit Sharma. This inventory consists of 80 items and each item having two alternatives i.e. yes or no, subject has to give their response by choosing one from yes or no alternative. This inventory reliability was split half (odd even method) 0.897 and test retest method was 0.927 and validity Co-efficient was found to be very high 0.834. The scoring of this inventory is very simple which can be scored simply by counting the number of correct answers marked in each area of adjustment. The sum of scores in difference area provides measure of total adjustment. High scores indicate poor adjustment and low scores indicate better adjustment.

Procedures of data collection

The following research methodology will be use in the present study. The primary information was gathered by giving personal information from to each to each student. The students were called in a small group of 10 to 15 students. To fill the inventories subjects were given general instructions belongs to each scale.

Data analysis

The data were analyzed as follows.

The Means and SD with graphical representation for gender and location on Bell's Adjustment Inventory was analyzed. 2x2 factorial design was selected to adequate of statistical analysis of 'F values in to examine the roll of main as well as subsequently on student's Adjustment.

Results and Discussion

Table No.01

Show the mean, SD and F value of Gender of Adjustment.

Gender	Mean	SD	N	DF	Mean Difference	F	Sign
Male Students	25.56	6.31	50	98	5.07	9.11	0.01
Female students	30.63	5.41	50				

Significant level of 'F' value: 0.05 level 7.08(df=98), 0.01 level 4.00 (df=98)

From table no.01 it was observed that the mean score of male college students is 25.56, and SD 6.31 and female college students whose mean score is 30.63 and SD 5.41, but on the basis of mean observation it would that mean difference 5.07 and 'F' values is 9.11, at a glance those female students shows high score than male students.

In the present study was first hypothesis related adjustment and Gender. It was "There is no significance difference between adjustment than male and female college students.

Gender effect represent the adjustment was significant ('F' value- 9.11, 1and 98, P- 0.05 and 0.01). This is significant 0.05 and 0.01 levels because they obtained 'F' value are high than table values at 0.05 and 0.01. In the present study was found that male and female college students differ from adjustment. The findings of the not supported the first hypothesis, they are first hypothesis rejected the present study. It indicates that gender significantly difference in adjustment.

Male 12th standard college student's high adjustment than Female 12th standard college students.

Table No.02**Show the mean, SD and F value of Location of Adjustment**

Location	Mean	SD	N	DF	Mean Difference	F	Sign
Urban Students	27.61	6.32	30	58	2.43	4.25	0.01
Rural Students	30.04	7.25	30				

Significant level of 'F' value: 0.05 level 7.08 (df=98), 0.01 level 4.00 (df=98)

From table no.02 it was observed that the mean score of urban college students is 27.61, and SD 6.32 and rural college students whose mean score is 30.04 and SD 7.25, but on the basis of mean observation it would that mean difference 2.43, and 'F' values is 4.25, at a glance those rural students shows high score than rural students.

In the present study was second hypothesis related adjustment and Location. It was "there is no significance difference between adjustment than Urban and Rural 12th standard college students."

Location effect represent the adjustment was significant ('F' value- 4.25, 1and 98, P- 0.05). This is significant 0.05 levels because they obtained F value are high than table values at 0.05. In the present study was found that urban and rural college students differ from adjustment. The findings of the not supported the second hypothesis, they are second hypothesis rejected the present study. It indicates that Location is significantly difference in adjustment.

Urban 12th standard college student's high adjustment than rural 12th standard college students.

Limitations of the study

- 1) The finding of the study is based on very sample.
- 2) The sample was restricted to Jalna city in Maharashtra.
- 3) The study was restricted to only 12th standard arts college students (arts facility) only.
- 4) The study was restricted students are only 18-19 years only.

Conclusion

- 1) Male 12th standard college student's high adjustment than Female 12th standard college students.

- 2) Urban 12th standard college student's high adjustment than rural 12th standard college students.

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